

A descriptive study on psycho-social problems of mothers having autistic children

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ABSTRACT

Parents' mental health could be intensively influenced by disabled child, especially when there is a disorder such as Autism including a wide range of behaviours and particularly social behaviours. Autistic disorder is one of the pervasive developmental disorders characterised by delay and deviance in the development of social, communicative and other skills, various motor mannerisms, resistance to change and idiosyncratic interests and preoccupations. Existing studies suggest that characteristics of the disorder cause stress in parents. Objectives of this study are to understand the socio-demographic details of the respondents, to understand the relationship between depression and age of the mother, to study the level of depression and to explore the impact of mother's education. The study is to understand the depression among the mothers having autistic children. In order to accomplish the objectives, the researcher has adopted descriptive design. The universe of the study considered by the researcher is the St. John of God special school, Maalam, Kottayam. The researcher adopted simple random sampling method and the size of the sample was 50. Data collection tool was questionnaire and parental stress scale were used in this study. The result of the study is majority of the respondents (64%) felt sad because of their child Autistic condition. Majority of the respondent (78%) are disappointed in themselves and they can't enjoy the things in their life. 44% of the respondents have moderate depression. Most of the respondents are less interested in other people that they used to be. 68% of the respondents are slightly more irritated than others.

Keywords: Autism, Depression, Motor mannerisms, Deviance, communicative skills.

1 INTRODUCTION

The word 'autism' comes from the Greek word 'autos', which means 'self'. It describes the conditions in which a person is removed from social interaction. In other words, he becomes an 'isolated self'. Autism is a complex neuro-behavioural condition that includes impairments in social interaction and developmental language and communication skills combined with rigid, repetitive behaviours. Because of the range of symptoms, this condition is now called autism spectrum disorder (ASD). It is estimated that worldwide there are 52 million people on the autism spectrum and research suggests that there is little variation from one region to another in the proportion of the population who are on the autism spectrum. March 2017 estimates of the number of people on the autism spectrum rely largely on the reported number of people who have received a diagnosis. Diagnosis is now more common in childhood and this means that the reported number of children with an autism diagnosis is higher than for adults.

Symptoms of Autism

Autism symptoms typically become clearly evident during early childhood, between 12 and 24 months of age. However, symptoms may also appear earlier or later. Early symptoms may include a marked delay in language or social development. The DSM-5 divides symptoms of autism into two categories: problems with communication and social interaction and restricted or repetitive patterns of behaviour or activities.

Communication difficulties

Some infants who later show signs of ASD and babble during the first few months of life, but they soon stop. Others may be delayed, developing languages as late as age 5 to 9. Some children may learn to use communication system such as pictures or sign language. Those who do speak often use language in unusual ways. They see unable to combine words into meaningful sentences. Some speak only single words, while others repeat the same phrase over and over. Some ASD children parrot what they hear, a condition called echolalia.

Problem with communication and social interaction includes issues with communication, difficulties in sharing emotions, difficulties in sharing interests, or maintaining a back- and -forth conversation. They have issues with non-verbal communication, such as trouble maintaining eye contact or reading body language. They make little or inconsistent eye contact. They tend not to look at or listen to people.

Repetitive behaviours

Although children with ASD usually appear physically normal and have good muscle control, odd repetitive motions may set them off from other children. These behaviours might be extreme and highly apparent or more subtle. Some children and older individuals spend a lot of time repeatedly flapping their arms or walking on their toes. Some suddenly freeze in position. As children, they might spend hours lining up their cars and trains in a certain way, rather than urine them for pretend play. If someone need and demand, absolute consistency in their

environment. A slight change in any routine – in meantime, dressing, taking a bath, going to school at a certain time and by the same route- can be extremely disturbing. Perhaps order and sameness lend some stability in a world of confusion. Repetitive behaviour sometimes takes the form of a persistent intense preoccupation.

Social symptoms

From the start, typically developing infants are social beings. Early in life, they gaze at people, turn toward voices, grasp a finger and even smile. In contrast, most children with ASD seem to have tremendous difficulty learning to engage in the give- and-take of everyday human interaction. Even in the first few months of life, many do not interact and they avoid eye contact. They seem indifferent to other people and often seem to prefer being alone. They may resist attention or passively accept hugs and cuddling. Later, they seldom seek comfort or respond to parents' displays of anger or affection in atypical way. Research has suggested that although children with ASD are attached to their parents, their expression of this attachment is unusual and difficult to read.

Sensory functioning

Young children with ASD frequently have sensory differences and may seek either sensory input or avoidance. Sensory differences often lead to over-responsiveness or under responsiveness to the environment. A typical sensory response may occur with any of the senses: visual, auditory, tactile, olfactory, or taste.

Language

Frequently, young children with ASD use their unique behavioural responses to communicate. Approximately 50% of children with autism never develop expressive verbal language with a communicative intent. They do not use language to socialise or facilitate having their needs met. Language delays can also include using language differently.

Cognitive functioning

Many children with ASD function with development resembling that of a much younger child. In early childhood, cognitive functioning is related to language, social, and motor development. Thus, if a child is delayed in more than one of these areas there is a strong chance that cognitive development may be delayed as well.

Aggressive behaviour and irritability

The causes of irritability and aggression are multifactorial: comprehension difficulties, decreased ability to communicate and express their needs and desires, reduced confrontation skills, conflict with colleagues and authority figures, Psycho-social dysfunction, undiagnosed pain, mood and anxiety disorders. Children with autism have trouble communicating. They have trouble understanding what other people think and feel. The main stressor for a parent is their child's inability to express their basic needs. This produce frustration for both the parent and child. The parent will experience difficulty clarifying the needs of their child diagnosed with autism while the child will experience difficulty expressing their own needs. This can often result in aggressive behaviors for the child diagnosed with ASD as parents may be u aware if their child is hungry, sick, tired, hurt, sad or mad. This is stressful for the children who are non - verbal.

II REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shripati Upadyaya et al (2009) conducted a study on autism spectrum disorders-service development issues. The study describes the development of an autism services in Branford, UK that has a population of nearly 450,000 of which 22% belong to ethnic minorities and a centre in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India that has a 31 population over 4 million. The authors emphasize that conceptual understanding of autism, awareness of specific needs of people with autism and involvement of a multi professional team are the key factors in providing an effective service for people with autism.

Salovita et al (2003) conducted studies on parents of children, with autism have shown that these parents, and in particular mothers are themselves at high risk of presenting mental health problems. A key element that might be involved in this process is stress. Indeed, there is considerable evidence that high levels of stress are associated with the task of caring for a child presenting different disabilities including autism.

III RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

- To understand the socio-demographic details of the respondent
- To understand the relationship between depression and age of the mother
- To study the level of depression
- To explore the impact of mother's education

The study is to understand the depression among the mothers having autistic children. In order to accomplish the objectives, the researcher has adopted descriptive design. The universe of the study considered by the researcher is the St. John of God special school, Maalam, Kottayam. The researcher adopted simple random sampling method and the size of the sample was 50. Data collection tool was questionnaire and parental stress scale were used in this study.

IV FINDINGS

Majority of the respondents (64%) felt sad about their child’s condition. Majority of the respondent (78%) are disappointed in themselves and they can’t enjoy the things in their life.44% of the respondents have moderate depression. But very less respondents have suicide tendency because of their child’s condition. They don’t feel this is because of God’s punishment. Most of the respondents are less interested in other people that they used to be.68% of the respondents are slightly more irritated than others.

table 1: distribution table shows that depression of mothers of autistic children.

OPTIONS	NO. OF RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
Fully Agreed	12	24%
Agree with Reservation	20	40%
Disagree with Reservation	8	16%
Fully Disagree	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Fig 1: Distribution chart represents problems in family due to deviant behaviour of the child

V DISCUSSION

An autism diagnosis can be perceived as a loss for the family. The grieving process associated with the birth of a child with disabilities is complicated by the parents’ grieving the death of the expected baby while at the same time trying to accept the imperfect baby. Even though they have the joy of being able to hold and love their baby, their life is suddenly and drastically changed. Most of the mothers are depressed in their children’s autistic condition. Majority of the respondents reported that their child belongs to the age group of 5-8 and 66% have male children. Most of the Mothers are not affected illness during the time of pregnancy. Parents experienced stress as a result to modifying goals and activities for their education as well as grief due to limited opportunities offered to their child.

VI SUGGESTIONS

- Celebrate the child's achievement even if they are small .
- Awareness and training classes should be provided to the parents. It will reduce their stress or anxiety about their child's future.
- Refer books, media for understanding the coping mechanisms used by the parents of autistic children.
- Try to know about the new educational facilities available for the autistic children.
- Local support group of mothers has to be encouraged .It will be helpful to share the experiences of autistic children and provides support each other.

VII CONCLUSION

Autism is associated with burden and depression in most of the mothers of the affected child. The demands placed by disability contribute to higher overall incidence of depression among mothers .It is significant for mothers to find coping mechanisms that work for them as they are needed to help find acceptance. There are different approaches and services available to mothers of children diagnosed with ASD which help alleviate some of the stressors families' experience. Social workers are needed to educate these families and provide them with appropriate resources.

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